

STUDY ON MARKETING OF WHEAT IN AMETHI DISTRICT OF UTTAR PRADESH

¹.Prabhat Tiwari ².Mr. Amit Kumar ³.Keshav Kant Thakur

1. P.G. Student MBA (agri bussiness)

Department Of Agricultural Economics,

Sam Higginbottom University of Agriculture, Technology And Sciences, Prayagraj, Uttar Pradesh, India

2. Assistant professor

Department Of Agricultural Economics

Sam Higginbottom University of Agriculture, Technology And Sciences, Prayagraj, Uttar Pradesh, India

3. P.G. Student MBA (agri bussiness)

Department Of Agricultural Economics,

Sam Higginbottom University of Agriculture, Technology And Sciences, Prayagraj, Uttar Pradesh, India.

(MS Received: 19.05.2023; MS Revised:22.06.2023; MS Accepted:23.06.2023)

MS 3059

(RESEARCH PAPER IN AGRICULTURAL ECONOMICS)

Abstract

The present study is based on Production and Marketing of Wheat in Amethi District, Uttar Pradesh. The present study was conducted in Amethi district of Uttar Pradesh plains. Out of 15 blocks of the district, Jamo block were selected randomly from five villages in the study. A sample of 120 farmers (63 small, 39 medium and 18 large) were selected from study area. The primary data from the farmers has been collected through personal interview method with the help of well prepared pre tested questionnaire for the year 2022-23. The canal was observed as a major source of irrigation. The average cropping intensity was observed 170.71 percent. The average size of holding of wheat growers was 1.40 hectares. Among different cost item contribution of total labour cost. To calculate the cost of cultivation, marketable surplus and disposal pattern of Wheat simple mean and average method was used. The channels of marketing of agriculture produce from producer to consumer vary from commodity to commodity and area to area. The chain of intermediaries through which product move from producer to consumer constitute their marketing channels. There were two common marketing channels identified in wheat in the study area. In this channel reveals that total marketing cost, marketing margin, price spread, Producers share in consumer rupee and marketing efficiency in both the marketing channels. The total market cost where higher in channel II (Rs.219.47) compared to channel (Rs.62.00) and the total marketing margin and price spread were also seen higher in channel II (Rs. 100,00), and (Rs.319.47) because in the channel II there are three intermediates where as in the channel I there is only one intermediate. The producer share in consumer rupee where higher in channel I 94.24 per cent. The marketing efficiency where higher in channel I 26.20per cent followed by channel II (5.34) respectively. Marketing of Wheat dependency of middle men for the disposal/sale of the produce and lack of regulated and cooperative market.

Key words- Wheat, Production and Marketing, farmers.

Introduction

Wheat is the main cereal crop in India. The total area under the crop is about 30.5 million hectares in the country. The production of wheat in the country has increased significantly from 75.81 million MT in 2006-07 to an all-time record high of 94.88 million MT in 2021-22 which reaches up to 106.84 MT which is more than average production of last five years. The productivity of wheat which was 2602 kg/hectare in 2004-05 has increased to 3140 kg/hectare in 2011-12. The major increase in the productivity of wheat has been observed in the states of Haryana, Punjab and Uttar Pradesh. Higher area coverage is reported from MP in recent years. Indian wheat is largely a soft/medium hard, medium protein, white bread wheat, somewhat similar to U.S. hard white wheat. Wheat grown in central and western India is typically hard, with high protein and high gluten content. India also produces around 1.0-1.2 million tons of durum wheat, mostly in the state of Madhya Pradesh. Most Indian durum is not marketed separately due to segregation problems in the market yards. However, some quantities are purchased by the private trade at a price premium; mainly for processing of higher value/branded products. The production and productivity of Wheat crop were quite low, when India became independent in 1947. The production of Wheat was only 6.46 million tones and productivity was merely 663 kg per hectare during 1950-51, which was not sufficient to feed the Indian population. The Country used to import Wheat in large quantities for fulfilling the needs of our people from many countries like USA under PL-480. The reasons of low production and productivity of Wheat at that time was (a) the tall growing plant habit resulting in lodging, when grown under fertile soils, (b) the poor tillering and low sink capacity of the varieties used, (c) higher susceptibility to diseases, (d) the higher sensitivity to thermo& photo variations, etc., resulting in poor adaptability, and (e) longer crop duration resulting in a long exposure of plants to the climatic variations and insect pest/disease attacks. The Government of India appointed a commission in 1961 to assess the feasibility of increasing the crop productivity under prevailing Indian ecological conditions. As result of various steps taken by Govt. of India, the Wheat scenario in our country has

completely changed. In the post-Independence era, country used to import Wheat for our needs but due to bumper increase in the production and productivity of Wheat in the 'Green Revolution' period in late sixties, our country became self-dependent in Wheat production. At present, country is 14 producing much more excess wheat than the requirement and godowns are over-flooded.

Wheat production in India

Wheat has distinct history in India. Considerable increase in wheat production during 60s led to green revolution in the country and makes the country self-sufficient in food grain. This significant contribution of wheat ushered Green Revolution in India, India produces around 100 million tons of wheat every year and stands at the third position in the list of the major wheat producers in the world. India also stands at the top in the world in terms of area covered in production of wheat. Uttar Pradesh is the leading producer state in India followed by Punjab and Haryana. Area, production and productivity of wheat in India during 2019 – 2020 and 2021-22 is shown in Uttar Pradesh, Madhya Pradesh, Punjab, Rajasthan, Bihar, Haryana, Maharashtra, and Gujarat are major wheat growing states in the country. Though the maximum acreage and production of wheat is in Uttar Pradesh but Punjab gives highest average yield per hectare (5004kg/ha) followed by Haryana (4831kg/ha). Wheat occupies a major share of 35% production in the total production of crops cultivated and 65% of total cropped area in the country. This share in production and area covered of the crop has increased since independence and is also constantly rising. The yield of wheat in kilograms per hectare has also risen significantly from 522kg/ha in 2000/01 to 1620kg/ha in 2008/09. Wheat is grown in India in an area of about 30 Million ha. with a production of 93 Million tones. The normal National productivity is about 2.98 tones/ha. These states contribute about 99.5% of total Wheat production in the country. The area, production and yield of wheat in different states of the country.

Research Methodology**Selection of district:**

There are 75 district in Uttar Pradesh out of which Amethi district was selected purposively due to maximum area in cultivation of

wheat. The wheat is one of the main crop in the district because climatic conditions are suitable for the cultivation of wheat.

Selection of Block

There are 13 Blocks in Amethi district in which. Jamo block was selected purposively for the study due to highest area under wheat cultivation. Jamo block is situated 35 Km away from the District Head Quarter on the Amethi. The agro-climatic condition of the block is suitable for the wheat cultivation.

Selection of villages:

There are 91 villages in Jamo block. A list of all villages along with area under wheat was obtained from the block development office. Out of these 5 % villages had been choose for the study purpose. Then all the villages were arranged in ascending order on the basis of cultivated area of wheat and five villages were selected randomly.

Section of respondents:

A complete list of all the respondents which were growing wheat was obtained from all selected villages. The study confined in the year

Result And Discussion

Table 1: Constraints in Marketing of Wheat in different Size of Farms Group

Si no	Particular	Size of farms group					Total in %	Rank
		Marginal	small	Semi-medium	medium	Large		
1	Lack of availability of market information at farm level	10	16	27	20	12	85 (70.83)	VI
2	Frequent price fluctuation	15	20	32	21	16	104 (86.66)	I
3	Lack of storage facility	10	12	14	9	5	50 (41.66)	XIII
4	Weighing loss during storage	14	16	22	14	10	78 (65.00)	VIII
5	High commission charges	16	19	28	22	14	99 (82.50)	IV
6	High transportation charges	14	20	30	21	18	103 (85.83)	II
7	Delay in cash payments	9	6	13	10	9	47 (39.16)	XIV
8	Lack of information about government schemes and subsidies	22	14	28	20	16	100 (83.33)	III
9	Lack of awareness of new technologies	18	14	26	17	21	86 (71.66)	V
10	Lack of support price when there is a glut in the market	15	8	18	16	17	64 (53.33)	XI
11	Loss due to lack of processing industries	26	9	20	15	6	76 (63.33)	IX
12	Lack of amenities and facilities	19	8	21	14	6	68 (56.66)	X
13	Lack of proper infrastructure in the market	19	7	14	8	3	51 (42.50)	XII
14	Lack of cooperatives in marketing societies at village level	26	10	18	15	14	83 (69.16)	VII

Table 1: reveal that constraints faced by the different size of farms group in marketing of wheat. Most of the Respondents expressed that major constraint was identified that Frequent price fluctuations and was assigned first rank followed by High transportation cost (11),Lack of information about government schemes and subsidies(III), High commission charges (IV),Lack of awareness of new technologies (V),Lack of availability of market information at farm level (VI),Lack of cooperatives in marketing societies at village level (VII), Weighing loss during storage (VIII),Loss due to highly perishable in nature which need food processing industries (IX),Lack of amenities and facilities in the market (X).Lack of support prices when there is a glut in the market (XI).Lack of proper infrastructure

2022-23. Therefore, the respondents were arranged in ascending order of area under cultivation .All together 10% of respondents were selected in all the 5 size farms groups in each randomly selected villages.

Selection of Market :- The primary and Secondary market will ne selected purposively for the present study.

Selection of market functionaries:-The study also intended to study the market functionaries at various level of marketing and their marketing efficiency. The detail of the marketing intermediaries was obtained from Agricultural office and and other sources. About 2 market intermediaries from all five villages market were interviewed, which include pre harvest contractor, agents, wholesalers, and retailers etc. A list of all wheat growers in five villages was prepared. The relevant information and data was collected from 120 wheat grower and 10 market intermediaries from the block were randomly selected making the total sample of 120.

in market (XII), Lack of storage facility (XIII) and finally Delay in cash payment which assigned least rank i.e. (XIV) respectively.

Conclusion

The study shows that marketing of Wheat in Amethi district. The main objective of the study is to analyze, socio economic characteristic of sample respondents, economics of Wheat processing, price spread and constraints In marketing of Wheat. The results revealing that the socio economic status of the respondents found to be moderate with primary education, well economic back ground and greater access to all the assets. The study indicated that there is scope to increase the producer's share in consumer's rupee by making the market more effective so that the number of

intermediaries is to be restricted and marketing costs and marketing margins to be reduced. This will be the way for making wheat cultivation more lucrative. Major constraints in marketing were price fluctuation followed by the lack of skilled labour in the study area. Marketing problems were frequent price fluctuations, high transportation charges and lack of information about government schemes and subsidies and lack of support prices when there is glut in market were the major problem faced by the different size of farms in marketing of wheat.

Suggestions

Regulated markets should be function throughout, at least in the busy agriculture harvesting seasons irrespective of holidays and thereby providing an opportunity for the producers to avail the facilities of Regulated Market. Regulated market yards should provided quality services and advance facilities to the farmers. The management of regulated market should be. Psychological and financial support should be given to the farmers that may encourage them by implementing advanced technology and machinery on large scale farming. Management of soil facility and micro nutrients should to made paper at appropriate time.

There is to need open new market centers within the reach of farmers. The co- operative societies can play important role in collecting even the small marketable surplus available with the farmers on procurement price fixed by government.

Storage facilities should be provided to the farmers in the mandi area and proper security of produce in needed. The grading and standardization facilities needed to be improved and strengthened immediately.

Various marketing facilities offered by regulated market committees in the principal yards market yards to the farmers should be extended effectively to cover the farmer residing in the remote village. It is necessary to open more regulated market and sub/feeder market yards preferably a yard for every five Gram Panchayats.

References

1. **Acharya, SS. Agrwal, N.L. (1999)** Agriculture marketing in India (Third edition) Oxford and IBH publishing Co. pvt Limited. New Delhi. Page No. 39

2. **Birthal. P.S. Taheja, V.K. and Thorope, W. (2006).** Smallholder livestock production.
3. **Bliyan, S.P. and Bhopal, T.S.(1996).** Resource use efficiency in ration crop of wheat in Western Uttar Pradesh. Indian wheat, Vol. 45, No. 12, PP. 943-949
4. **Chapman, L.S., Wilson, J.R., Wilson, I.R., Hogarth, D.M., Campbell, J.A. and Garside, A.L(1996).** Economics of ratoon cycle length in wheat. wheat 2000 Symposium, wheat, research towards efficient and Sustainable Production, PP. 163-171. Goel, V. (2011) Various sized wheat growers' asset positions, cultivable practices and chain coordination mechanisms in Punjab, India. ActaHorticulturae;.895,129-136.
5. **Dondyal, S.P. (1954).** Farm management- An Economic analysis. Aman publications.
6. **Government of U.P. (2008).** Agriculture statistics 2006-2007.Department of economics and statistics, Vikas Bhawan, maharajanj U.P.
7. **Jyaraman, S., Alagudurai, S. and Kannappan, K. (2002).**Measures to reduce the cost of wheat cultivation. Indian wheat, Vol. 52. No.9, pp. 689-694.
8. **Joshi, A.S., Bhullar, A.S., Sharma, V.K. and Kingra, H.S. (2003).** A study into the Economics of Farming and the Pattern of Income and Expenditure Distribution in the Punjab Agriculture.Project report, submitted to Punjab Agricultural University, Ladhiana, P. 84.
9. **Kole, P.V. and Sale. D.L. (1999)** Resource productivities of wheat crop in Western Maharashtra. Indian wheat, Vol. 49. (3), pp. 203-208.
10. **Kole, P.V., Kadad, B.S., Aha, T.D. and sale, D.L. (1999)** Cost and return structure of wheat in Western Maharashtra, Indian wheat, Vol. 49, 1 pp. 713-721.
11. **Malik, S.K. and Sing, R.R. (2000).**Breakup of cost and returns of wheat production in reserve and free area of wheat Mill. Indian wheat vol. 55,pp. 355-360.